

Workflow for CLEM image correlation with ec-CLEM (Icy)

Start Icy software

Start ec-CLEM plugin
under “Plugins”

ec-CLEM prompt after start. Load images to be overlaid.

Select 2D (but let me update myself) and the images. Transformed image (LM) and fixed image (EM). Then press play.

The screenshot displays the Icy software interface. At the top, there are tabs for 'Image / Sequence', 'Region Of Interest', 'ImageJ', 'Detection & Tracking', 'Processing', 'Tools', and 'Plugins'. Below these are toolbars for 'Online plugin', 'Setup', and 'Other Plugins'. Two image windows are open: 'B97_1_F10_02_CH4.tif' on the left, showing a fluorescence microscopy image with green and blue channels, and 'B97_1_F10_003_M.tif' on the right, showing a grayscale electron microscopy image. Both windows have a '2D' dropdown menu and various view controls. On the right side, there is a 'Canvas' panel with a zoom of 100%, a rotation of 0 degrees, and a histogram and colormap panel. Below the image windows is a dialog box titled 'ec-CLEM' (Version 1.0.1.5). The dialog has a dropdown menu set to '2D but let me update myself'. Below this are buttons for 'I want to preprocess my data', 'I want to apply a previously computed transfo', and 'Advanced usage'. Under 'Images to process', there are two dropdown menus: 'Select image that will be transformed and resized (likely FM)' set to 'B97_1_F10_02_CH4.tif' and 'Select image that will not be modified (likely EM)' set to 'B97_1_F10_003_M.tif'. At the bottom of the dialog, there are buttons for 'Update Transformation', 'Clear all landmarks points', 'Undo last point', and 'Show ROIs on original source image'. A red box highlights the '2D but let me update myself' dropdown, the two image selection dropdowns, and a play button at the bottom left of the dialog. The Icy logo and version number (2.4.3.0) are visible in the bottom right corner. A system tray at the very bottom shows 'Memory: 1.5 GB / 88.6 GB', 'CPU: 0%', and 'Cache disabled'.

All points MUST be added to the target image (EM)!
Use the mouse wheel to navigate by zooming in and out. Left click ONLY for adding points.

The screenshot displays the Icy software interface. At the top, there are menu tabs: Image / Sequence, Region Of Interest, ImageJ, Detection & Tracking, Processing, Tools, and Plugins. Below these are toolbars for Online plugin, Setup, and Other Plugins. The main workspace contains two image windows: 'B97_1_F10_02_CH4.tif (transformed)' on the left and 'B97_1_F10_003_M.tif' on the right. The left window shows a blue and green fluorescence image with a 10 µm scale bar and coordinates X 1302.6, Y 714, Value 11: 64: 162. The right window shows a grayscale electron microscopy image with a 10 µm scale bar and coordinates X 3009.3, Y 6770.9, Value 143. A red box highlights the right window with the text 'Target Mask can add ROI points here'. To the right of the image windows is a 'Canvas' panel with a zoom of 100% and rotation of 0 degrees. Below the canvas is a 'Histogram and colormap' panel with a histogram and a color bar. At the bottom of the interface is a dialog box titled 'ec-CLEM' (Version 1.0.1.5). The dialog has a dropdown menu set to '2D but let me update myself' and several buttons: 'I want to preprocess my data', 'I want to apply a previously computed transfo', and 'Advanced usage'. Under 'Images to process', there are two dropdown menus: 'Select image that will be transformed and resized (likely FM)' set to 'B97_1_F10...ansformed' and 'Select image that will not be modified (likely EM)' set to 'B97_1_F10_003_M.tif'. There are also buttons for 'Update Transformation', 'Clear all landmarks points', 'Undo last point', and 'Show ROIs on original source image'. At the bottom of the dialog are checkboxes for 'Show Difference in Positions', 'Show Predicted Error in Positions', 'Compute the whole predicted error map', and 'Monitor a target point'. The Icy logo and version number 'Version 2.4.3.0' are visible in the bottom right corner. A system tray at the very bottom shows 'Memory: 1.6 GB / 88.6 GB', 'CPU: 0%', and 'Cache disabled'.

After adding a point to the TEM image it is added to the center of the LM image and needs to be dragged to the correct position. Then press “Update Transformation”

The screenshot displays the Icy software interface. At the top, the menu bar includes Image / Sequence, Region Of Interest, ImageJ, Detection & Tracking, Processing, Tools, and Plugins. Below the menu is a toolbar with various icons for image manipulation and analysis. The main workspace is divided into two image windows. The left window, titled 'B97_1_F10_003_M.tif', shows a grayscale transmission electron micrograph (TEM) of biological structures with a 'Point 1' marker. The right window, titled 'B97_1_F10_02_CH4.tif (transformed)', shows a corresponding color image with a 'Point 1' marker. Both windows include a 10 µm scale bar and coordinate information (X, Y, Value). To the right of the image windows is a 'Canvas' panel with a zoomed-in view of the 'Point 1' marker, a histogram and colormap, and a color selection tool. Below the image windows is a dialog box titled 'ec-CLEM' (Version 1.0.1.5). The dialog box has a dropdown menu set to '2D but let me update myself' and three buttons: 'I want to preprocess my data', 'I want to apply a previously computed transfo', and 'Advanced usage'. Under the 'Images to process' section, there are two dropdown menus: 'Select image that will be transformed and resized (likely FM)' set to 'B97_1_F10_...ansformed' and 'Select image that will not be modified (likely EM)' set to 'B97_1_F10_003_M.tif'. A red box highlights the 'Update Transformation' button. Other buttons in the dialog include 'Clear all landmarks points', 'Undo last point', 'Show ROIs on original source image', 'Show Difference in Positions', 'Show Predicted Error in Positions', 'Compute the whole predicted error map', and 'Monitor a target point'. The bottom of the dialog shows a 'Running' status bar. In the bottom right corner, the Icy logo and version number 'Version 2.4.3.0' are visible, along with system resource indicators: 'Memory: 1.2 GB / 88.6 GB', 'CPU: 0%', and 'Cache disabled'.

Add a second point in a similar way.

The screenshot displays the Icy software interface. At the top, there are menu tabs: Image / Sequence, Region Of Interest, ImageJ, Detection & Tracking, Processing, Tools, and Plugins. Below the menus is a toolbar with various icons for image manipulation and analysis. The main workspace is divided into two image windows. The left window, titled 'B97_1_F10_003_M.tif', shows a grayscale electron micrograph of biological structures with a scale bar of 10 μm. A yellow dot labeled 'Point 1' is marked on a structure. The right window, titled 'B97_1_F10_02_CH4.tif (transformed)', shows a false-color image of the same area with a scale bar of 10 μm. A green dot labeled 'Point 2' is marked on a structure. To the right of the image windows is a panel with 'Canvas', 'Histogram and colormap', and 'Sequence Properties' sections. The 'Sequence Properties' section shows details for the current image: Name: B97_1_F10_02_CH4.tif (transformed), Path: B97_1_F10_02_CH4.tif (transformed).tif, Dimension: 1360 x 1024 x 1 x 1, Channel: 3, Data type: 8 bits, Size: 4.1 MB, Date: Unknow, Time interval: 1sec 0.0ms, Pixel size: 0.16um, 0.16um, 1.0um. At the bottom of the interface is the 'ec-CLEM' dialog box, version 1.0.1.5. It has a dropdown menu set to '2D but let me update myself' and several buttons: 'I want to preprocess my data', 'I want to apply a previously computed transfo', and 'Advanced usage'. Under 'Images to process', there are two dropdown menus: 'Select image that will be transformed and resized (likely FM)' set to 'B97_1_F10_...ansformed' and 'Select image that will not be modified (likely EM)' set to 'B97_1_F10_003_M.tif'. A red box highlights the 'Update Transformation' button. Other buttons include 'Clear all landmarks points', 'Undo last point', 'Show ROIs on original source image', 'Show Difference in Positions', 'Show Predicted Error in Positions', 'Compute the whole predicted error map', and 'Monitor a target point'. The status bar at the bottom indicates 'Running'.

Add a third point in a similar way.

The screenshot displays the Icy software interface with two main image windows and a plugin window. The left window shows a grayscale electron micrograph of a biological specimen with a yellow dot labeled 'Point 3' and a 10 µm scale bar. The right window shows the same specimen after transformation, appearing as a blue and green heatmap, also with a yellow dot labeled 'Point 3' and a 10 µm scale bar. The bottom window is the 'ec-CLEM' plugin, which is used for image registration. It includes a dropdown menu for 'I want to compute the transformation in:' set to '2D but let me update myself', and buttons for 'I want to preprocess my data', 'I want to apply a previously computed transfo', and 'Advanced usage'. Under 'Images to process', it lists 'B97_1_F10...ansformed' as the image to be transformed and 'B97_1_F10_003_M.tif' as the reference image. The 'Update Transformation' button is highlighted with a red box. The right sidebar shows the 'Sequence' and 'Canvas' panels, including a histogram and colormap. The bottom right corner shows system information: 'Memory: 28 GB / 68 GB', 'CPU: 18%', and 'Cache disabled'. The Icy logo is visible in the bottom right, and a status bar at the very bottom indicates 'Applying the transformation...'.

After adding the third point pair and updating, the LM image will be transformed.

The screenshot displays the Icy software interface with two main image windows and a dialog box. The left window, titled "B97_1_F10_003_M.tif", shows a grayscale electron microscopy image with three yellow point pairs labeled "Point 1", "Point 2", and "Point 3". A scale bar at the bottom indicates 10 μm. The right window, titled "B97_1_F10_02_CH4.tif (transformed)", shows the same image after transformation, appearing as a bright green and blue structure against a dark blue background, with the same three point pairs. A scale bar at the bottom indicates 10 μm. The bottom window is the "ec-CLEM" dialog box, version 1.0.1.5, which is used for image registration. It has a dropdown menu set to "2D but let me update myself" and buttons for "I want to preprocess my data", "I want to apply a previously computed transfo", and "Advanced usage". Under "Images to process", it shows "Select image that will be transformed and resized (likely FM)" set to "B97_1_F10...ansformed" and "Select image that will not be modified (likely EM)" set to "B97_1_F10_003_M.tif". There are buttons for "Update Transformation", "Clear all landmarks points", "Undo last point", and "Show ROIs on original source image". At the bottom, there are checkboxes for "Show Difference in Positions", "Show Predicted Error in Positions", "Compute the whole predicted error map", and "Monitor a target point". The Icy logo and version 2.4.3.0 are visible in the bottom right corner. A status bar at the very bottom shows "Running" and system information: "Memory: 9.0 GB / 88.6 GB", "CPU: 5%", and "Cache disabled".

Now add more points.
The more points the better the correlation.
Always press "Update Transformation" after each point pair.
When done, press the stop button.

The screenshot displays the Icy software interface with two image windows and a dialog box. The left window shows a grayscale image with 10 yellow landmark points labeled Point 1 through Point 10. The right window shows the same image after transformation, with the points now aligned. The ec-CLEM dialog box is open, showing the 'Update Transformation' button highlighted with a red box. The dialog box includes fields for image selection and processing options.

Image Windows:

- B97_1_F10_003_M.tif:** Target image. X: 6839.2, Y: 6553.6, Value: 138. Scale bar: 10 um.
- B97_1_F10_02_CH4.tif (transformed):** Source image. X: 6839.2, Y: 6553.6, Value: 8 : 64 : 150. Scale bar: 10 um.

ec-CLEM Dialog Box:

- Version: 1.0.1.5
- I want to compute the transformation in: 2D but let me update myself
- I want to preprocess my data
- I want to apply a previously computed transfo
- Advanced usage
- Images to process:
 - Select image that will be transformed and resized (likely FM): B97_1_F10_...ansformed
 - Select image that will not be modified (likely EM): B97_1_F10_003_M.tif
- Buttons: Update Transformation, Clear all landmarks points, Undo last point, Show ROIs on original source image
- Options: Show Difference in Positions, Show Predicted Error in Positions, Compute the whole predicted error map, Monitor a target point
- Status: Running

Right Panel:

- Canvas: Shows the transformed image.
- Zoom: 100%
- Rotation: 0°
- Histogram and colormap: Shows a histogram and a color map.
- Sequence Properties:
 - Name: B97_1_F10_02_CH4.tif (transformed)
 - Path: B97_1_F10_02_CH4.tif (transformed).tif
 - Dimension: 9620 x 7132 x 1 x 1
 - Channel: 3, Data type: 8 bits
 - Size: 201.0 MB, Owner(s):
 - Date: Unknow, Time interval: 1sec 0.0ms
 - Pixel size: 8.7nm, 8.7nm, 1.0um

System Information:

- Memory: 80 GB / 68 GB
- CPU: 1%
- Cache disabled

An overlaid image will appear. If that looks good, you can ignore the error message.

The screenshot displays the Icy software interface with several windows and panels. At the top, the menu bar includes 'Image / Sequence', 'Region Of Interest', 'ImageJ', 'Detection & Tracking', 'Processing', 'Tools', and 'Plugins'. Below the menu is a toolbar with various icons for image manipulation and analysis. The main workspace contains two image windows: 'B97_1_F10_003_M.tif' and 'B97_1_F10_02_CH4.tif (transformed)'. The 'Overlaid' window shows the two images combined, with a cyan-colored structure overlaid on a blue background. A 'Confirmation' dialog box is open in the center, displaying a warning message about registration error and an 'OK' button. At the bottom, the 'ec-CLEM' dialog box is visible, showing options for image processing and transformation. The right side of the interface features a 'Canvas' panel with zoom and rotation controls, a 'Histogram and colormap' panel, and a 'Sequence Properties' panel with a table of image metadata. The bottom right corner shows the Icy logo and system status information.

Confirmation

Based on the discrepancy between observed error and predicted error, computed from the landmark configuration you have used, Either this image DOES require deformable registration, Either at least one landmark is (really) badly placed. You can use the "show difference in position" to detect it. Check the position of your landmarks pair, select "Non Rigid Correction" in the list of transform, and click on update transform

OK

ec-CLEM

Version 1.0.1.5

I want to compute the transformation in: 2D but let me update myself

I want to preprocess my data

I want to apply a previously computed transfo

Advanced usage

Images to process

Select image that will be transformed and resized (likely FM) B97_1_F10_...ansformed

Select image that will not be modified (likely EM) B97_1_F10_003_M.tif

Update Transformation Clear all landmarks points Undo last point Show ROIs on original source image

Show Difference in Positions Show Predicted Error in Positions Compute the whole predicted error map Monitor a target point

Sequence Properties

Name	Overlaid
Dimension	9620 x 7132 x 1 x 1
Channel	4
Data type	8 bits
Size	268.0 MB
Owner(s)	Gunar-P52
Date	Unknow
Time interval	1sec 0.0ms
Pixel size	8.7nm 8.7nm 1.0um

Memory: 64 GB / 68 GB
CPU: 3%
Cache disabled

Icy
Version 2.4.3.0

Adjust the histogram and save the image. It is important to adjust the histogram of the LM channels here as a new image with adjusted fluorescence intensities will be created which are not easy to change later on.

The screenshot displays the Icy software interface with several key components:

- Top Panel:** A menu bar with options like 'Image / Sequence', 'Region Of Interest', 'ImageJ', 'Detection & Tracking', 'Processing', 'Tools', and 'Plugins'. Below it are various tool buttons for file operations (Open, Duplicate, Save as...), conversion (Conversion, Raw conversion), and image manipulation (Fast crop, Canvas size, Image size, Extract, Remove, Merge, Reverse order, Extract slice, Remove slice, Extract frame, Remove frame, Add, Merge, Convert to stack, Convert to time, Advanced...).
- Main View:** Two image windows are visible. The top window shows a fluorescence image with a green line and colored spots. The bottom window shows a grayscale image with a green line and a 10 µm scale bar. A 'Save image file' dialog is overlaid on the top window, showing a list of files and a 'Speichern in' field set to 'example4_2D_CLEM'. The 'Dateiname' is 'Overlaid' and 'Dateityp' is 'TIFF images (*.tif, *.tiff)'. A 'Histogram and colormap' window is also open, showing a histogram with a value of 255.0 and pixel number 751.
- Right Panel:** A 'Sequence Properties' panel is visible, showing details for the 'Overlaid' sequence. It includes fields for 'Dimension' (9620 x 7132 x 1 x 1), 'Channel' (4), 'Data type' (8 bits), 'Size' (268.0 MB), 'Date' (Unknown), 'Time interval' (1sec 0.0ms), and 'Pixel size' (8.7nm x 8.7nm x 1.0um). There are buttons for 'Edit' and 'Metadata'.
- Bottom Panel:** A 'Processing' panel titled 'ec-CLEM' is visible, showing options for 'I want to compute the transformation in:' (2D but let me update myself), 'I want to preprocess my data', 'I want to apply a previously computed transfo', and 'Advanced usage'. It also has fields for 'Select image that will be transformed and resized (likely FM)' and 'Select image that will not be modified (likely EM)'. There are buttons for 'Update Transformation', 'Clear all landmarks points', 'Undo last point', 'Show ROIs on original source image', 'Show Difference in Positions', 'Show Predicted Error in Positions', 'Compute the whole predicted error map', and 'Monitor a target point'.